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D6.1. Evaluation design and plan report

WP 6 Assessment and data analysis

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¹ PU= Public

EVALUATION DESIGN AND PLAN REPORT

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GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

AARP	American Association of Retired Persons
ADL	Activities of Daily Living
BIA	Budget Impact Analysis
CDSE	Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy
CDSMP	Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme
CHU	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire
CIRS	Cumulative Illness Rating Scale
DSM	Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of mental disorders
EFFICHRONIC	enhancing health systems sustainability by providing (cost-) Effectiveness data of an evidenced-based Intervention for CHRONIC management in citizens with a low socioeconomic status
EU	European Union
EQ-5D-5L	EuroQoL- 5 Dimensions - 5 Levels
FICYT	Fundación para el Fomento en Asturias de la Investigación Científica Aplicada y la Tecnología
GA	Grant Agreement
HLQ	Health Literacy Questionnaire
HR-QoL	Health-Related Quality of Life
IADL	Instrumental Activities of Daily Living
ICPC	International Classification of Primary Care
IPAQ	International Physical Activity Questionnaire
MNA	Mini Nutritional Assessment
M+ number	Months in the EFFICHRONIC project
MPI	Multidimensional Prognostic Index
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NL	The Netherlands
PCQ	Productivity Costs Questionnaire
PHQ	Patient Health Questionnaire
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
QISMET	Quality Institute for Self-Management Education & Training
SD	Standard Deviation
SEP	Socio Economic Position
SF	Short-Form
SFES	Social-Familial Evaluation Scale
SMAQ	Short Medication Adherence Questionnaire
SMRC	Self-Management Resource Center
TYM	Test Your Memory
UVEG	University of Valencia
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

SECTION 1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

INTRODUCTION

EFFICHRONIC is a project funded by the Third EU Health Programme (2014-2020; <http://effichronic.eu/>) and deals with one of its priorities, that is, to reduce the burden of major chronic diseases and increase the sustainability of health systems by providing evidence on the cost-efficiency of investments in evidenced-based prevention and management programme for chronic conditions by integrating social determinants of health. In the project, pilot sites in five European countries (the region of Occitanie in France, the province of Genoa in Italy, the region of Rotterdam in the Netherlands, several areas in the UK and Principality of Asturias in Spain), implement the Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme (CDSMP) specifically in citizens with chronic conditions and caregivers from vulnerable populations. The CDSMP intervention is an evidence-based program for adults with a chronic condition to encourage them to better manage their health and maintain their health status.

Using a 6-month pre-post design, 2,000 citizens ≥ 18 years of age with a chronic condition and caregivers with a low socio-economic position (400 participants in each country) are recruited to receive the CDSMP intervention. The effects of the intervention in terms of self-management in healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, adherence to medications and health-related quality of life (HR-QoL), and in terms of experienced medical errors, communication with healthcare providers and health literacy are measured. The analyses include a preliminary cost-effectiveness analysis performed from a societal and healthcare perspective with a time horizon of 6 months.

OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

In this deliverable, 2 main aspects of EFFICHRONIC are covered: on the one hand, to describe the evaluation framework with the chosen instruments used for data collection and on the other hand, to evaluate the training of the CDSMP as described in task 5.2. 'Preparation of the intervention programme including training of the CDSMP monitors' and 5.3 'Implementation of the CDSMP'.

The specific objectives of the deliverable regarding the evaluation framework are: to report on the joint work and the methodologies used for the elaboration of the evaluation framework, to describe the used health indicators and the variables in six dimensions and to explain the statistical analysis design.

The specific objectives of this deliverable regarding the implementation of the CSDMP are: to explain and establish the basis for the CSDMP implementation, to report on the CDSMP implementation phase and to evaluate the training and the preliminary results obtained until the submission date of this deliverable (M24).

METODOLOGY

This report covers the design of the evaluation framework and the preliminary results of the CDSMP implementation from M10 to M24. It is based on information from the bimonthly activities reports of all partners, the newsletters, the bulletins, the virtual and face-to-face meetings, all registered in a central data base. In this regard, data have been recovered from the internal reports stored in a central repository kept by the Project Coordinator and from internal repositories at each study site.

KEY FINDINGS

The key results regarding the evaluation framework are:

- The design of the evaluation methodology and description of instruments
- The establishment of the analysis plan to for statistical and health economic final plan
- Agreement on an evaluative model with six main constructs (outcomes).

The key results of the CDSMP implementation are:

- Elaboration of the training material adapted and translated to the different languages of the consortium
- Successful achievement of training the minimum number of necessary Leaders by all partners (32) which ensures the efficacious implementation of the workshops
- Successful dissemination strategy to recruit the target population
- Lower than expected level of completion of the questionnaires in the vulnerable population.

CONCLUSIONS

Most of the performance indicators regarding the evaluation design and the implementation have been fulfilled according to Annex I of the Grant Agreement at M24. The designed evaluation framework responds to all the specific objectives and outcomes described in the EFFICHRONIC. The efforts made by all consortium members facilitated overcoming the difficulties to successfully implement the CDSMP programme in vulnerable population at European level. There are differences in the implementation rate between the partners mainly due to different starting points concerning CDSMP experience.

RECOMMENDATIONS

For future research projects involving the implementation of a self-management programme, or any health promotion programme for that matter, it is recommended to estimate the target number of included subjects in an individualized manner, taking into account previous programme experience and available resources.

Another recommendation is to add qualitative studies to measure results in vulnerable population, given the difficulty to obtain sufficient quantitative information through self-administered questionnaires in this specific target population.

SECTION 2: PURPOSE, OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE

PURPOSE

The aims of this deliverable are:

1. To describe the elaboration of the evaluation framework to assess health outcomes and cost-efficiency results (WP6).
2. To explain the preparation and implementation of the intervention programme in 2,000 citizens with a chronic disease and caregivers from vulnerable populations, including the training of the CDSMP monitors in the framework of the EFFICHRONIC project.

This deliverable contains useful information for:

- The project management team on the status of the evaluation framework and the implementation progress at M24 to have an overview of the progress of the project.
- For other Regional or National Authorities interested in the implementation of the CDSMP.
- For research organizations working with vulnerable population and/or recruitment strategies.

OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives of this deliverable regarding the evaluation framework are:

1. To report on the joint work of all partners and the used methodologies for the elaboration of the evaluation framework.
2. To identify the health indicators and the variables that allow to answer the following questions:
 - a) What are the benefits of the CDSMP intervention for the target population in terms of self-management in healthy lifestyle, depression, sleep and fatigue, adherence to medications and Health-Related Quality of Life (HR-QoL)?
 - b) What are the effects of the CDSMP intervention for the target population on the prevalence of experienced medical errors, communication with healthcare providers and health literacy?
 - c) What are the societal cost savings of the CDSMP intervention in terms of reducing healthcare utilization and productivity losses among the target population?
 - d) To what extent is the target population satisfied with the CDSMP intervention as a whole as well as with specific elements (problem solving, decision making, and confidence building)?
3. To describe the statistical analysis design.

The specific objectives of this deliverable regarding the CSDMP implementation are:

1. To explain and establish the basis for the CSDMP implementation, which includes the training of monitors in the five consortium countries.
2. To report on the progression of the CDSMP implementation up to M24 in the five countries.
3. To evaluate the training and the results obtained until the submission date of this deliverable.

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Note: In deliverable D5.1 “CDSMP Implementation Plan”, due in M28, the full implementation will be described in detail.

Study hypotheses

We hypothesize that the intervention will provide participants with a greater ability to self-manage their chronic condition, a more favorable lifestyle, less depression, sleeping problems and fatigue, greater adherence to medication and a more favorable HR-QoL. We also hypothesize that the intervention will reduce the prevalence of experienced medical errors and improve the communication with healthcare providers and health literacy. We furthermore hypothesize that society will benefit from the intervention through a reduced use of healthcare resources and greater productivity. We hypothesize to reach a satisfaction score of 7 or higher on a 1–10 scale, with higher scores representing greater satisfaction.

SCOPE

The evaluation framework and CDSMP implementation was designed specifically to be used within the Project EFFICHRONIC, taking into consideration the specific demands that correspond to the particularities of the project design: working with vulnerable people on the one hand and on the other, implementing a chronic disease self-management programme.

SECTION 3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

Design, setting and procedures

The evaluation study of the EFFICHRONIC project has a pre-post design. Data will be collected from participants before the start of the first workshop session (baseline; T0) and at 6 months (T1).

The recruitment strategies were described in detail in D4.2 “Ethics, methodologies and standards” which was due by M12 (May 2018). Enrolling the target population is performed in accordance with the capacity, organizational and contextual factors of each of the five pilot sites. Additionally, to be more efficient in recruiting, vulnerability maps were constructed in some regions (region of Occitanie, province of Genoa and principality of Asturias), detecting EUROSTAT NUT-3 level geographical areas in which the prevalence of the target population is high.

A newly developed tool, the selfy-MPI, was used to stratify the target population. This tool is based on the Multidimensional Prognostic Index (MPI), as detailed in Deliverable D4.1 “List of clinical and social variables and MPI index” also produced in May 2018. The new selfy-MPI was tested in our target population as a stratification instrument.

Study population and eligibility to participate in the study

We aim to involve 400 participants in each country. In total, 2,000 participants will be included. The target population consists of citizens ≥ 18 years of age with a chronic condition and caregivers with a vulnerability profile and who are expected to be able to participate in the study for at least 6 months. The chronic condition (self-reported or clinically diagnosed by medical staff) is defined as 1) a chronic pathology with code between 70 and 99 registered in one of the 17 chapters of the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC-2) and 2) more than six months of evolution. Citizens are not eligible to participate when they are not able to understand the information provided in the language of the country of residence, when they are experiencing a period of crisis (e.g. domestic violence, impending eviction), when their basic housing needs are not met (e.g. being homeless), when they are diagnosed with severe unstable mental health problems (DSM V; e.g. psychosis), when they suffer from active addictive disorders (e.g. alcohol addiction) or from cognitive decline (e.g. Alzheimer). The number of participants per series of workshops will be no more than 20. Written consent is acquired from all participants.

Data-collection and measures

Data collection is done with the use of an auto-administrable baseline (Annex 1) and follow-up (Annex 2) questionnaire, elaborated in the local languages of the five countries. The instruments for which no

validated translations were available have been translated. Translations were discussed by the study team and adapted when needed. Before the start of the study, the questionnaire has been pilot-tested in all participating sites to assure its user-friendliness in terms of appropriateness, comprehensibility and length.

A variety of outcome measures is examined. The **primary objective** is to evaluate the 6-month improvement of self-management in healthy life style, depression, sleep and fatigue, adherence to medications and HR-QoL. Self-management is measured with the short 6-item version of the Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument (CDSE-6; developed specifically for the CDSMP intervention), which measures the confidence in one's ability to deal with health problems. It covers domains that are common across many chronic conditions, such as symptom control, role function, emotional functioning and communicating with physicians. Healthy life style is measured with six items on physical exercise (developed specifically for the CDSMP intervention), three items on healthy eating (intake of fruits, vegetables, and breakfast), one item from the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) on sedentary behaviour, one item on smoking and one item from the AUDIT-C on alcohol use. Depression is measured with the 8-item Patient Health Questionnaire depression scale (PHQ-8). Sleep and fatigue are measured by visual analog scales (developed specifically for the CDSMP intervention). Participants are asked to indicate how they experience the severity of their sleeping problems and fatigue during the last week on a scale from 0 (no sleeping problem/fatigue) to 10 (severe sleeping problem/fatigue). Adherence to medication is measured with six items from the Short Medication Adherence Questionnaire (SMAQ), a short tool based on questions posed directly to the participant regarding his/her medication-taking habits. HR-QoL is measured with the 12-item short-form (SF-12) and the EuroQol 5D-5L instrument. The SF-12 is a patient-reported survey which includes both a Physical Component Summary Scale (physical functioning, role-physical, pain and general health) and a Mental Component Summary Scale (vitality, social functioning, role-emotional, and mental health). The EQ-5D-5L is often used in health economics as a variable in the quality-adjusted life year calculation to determine the cost-effectiveness of an intervention. It has five dimensions: mobility, self-care, activity, pain and anxiety. Each dimension has five levels, ranging from no problems (level 1) to serious problems (level 5). Hence, EQ-5D-5L has 3,125 possible health states. Utility values for these health states are available for the pilot sites of each participating country. As part of the EQ-5D, participants are also asked to indicate their experienced current health state on a visual analog scale, 0 being the worst imaginable health and 100 being the best imaginable health.

A **secondary set** of outcome measures concern the prevalence of experienced medical errors, communication with healthcare providers and health literacy. The prevalence of experienced medical errors is measured with 3 items from the American Association of Retired Persons (AARP) 'survey beyond 50.09' questionnaire. Communication with healthcare providers is measured with a scale of 3 items which measures the change in key behaviours concerning communicating with healthcare providers, a scale developed by the Self-Management Resource Center (SMRC) previously known as The Stanford Patient Education Research Center. Health literacy is measured with 2 questions from the Health Literacy Questionnaire (HLQ), which was designed using a validity-driven approach and which is used in many countries and in many settings.

The **third objective** is to assess the societal cost savings of the CDSMP intervention in terms of healthcare utilization and productivity. Healthcare utilization is measured with 4 questions from the SMRC Health Care Utilization questionnaire regarding doctor appointments, the use of hospital emergency

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rooms and hospital admissions. Productivity losses are measured with two domains from the Productivity Costs Questionnaire (PCQ): Lost productivity at paid work due to absenteeism (6 items) and lost productivity at unpaid work (3 items).

Finally, various socio-demographic characteristics are measured, such as age, gender, country of birth, educational level and employment situation. Any additional remarks can be left in an open box at the end of the questionnaire.

The T0 and T1-questionnaire are almost identical, with the exception of seven additional items which measure the general satisfaction of the target population with the intervention. In the T1-questionnaire, four items measure the experienced improvement in specific elements (problem solving, decision making, and confidence building), one additional item relates to the participants' confidence in their national health system, another refers to improvement of interpersonal communication skills and a sixth supplementary item rates the satisfaction with the whole CDSMP intervention on a scale from 1 to 10.

Power considerations

In a study on the effect of the application of the CDSMP, the sub-score “well-being” and “energy” of the SF-36 improved with 6.0 +/- 19.1 and 4.3 +/- 23.2, respectively after six months. The lowest Cohen's d is therefore of 0.185 in quality of life's domains. In our study, we wish to demonstrate a statistically significant difference on the two subscales of the SF-12 in the fiveparticipating countries. Thus, the principal conclusion of the study will rely on 10 tests. Therefore, we apply the Bonferroni's correction on the significance threshold, and we will consider an alpha risk of 0.005 for the tests of the primary objective. To show a statistically significant effect size of 0.185, with a bilateral alpha risk of 0.005, a power of 0.9, and a correlation between T0 and 6 months of 0, by a paired Student's t-test, we need to analyze 978 subjects. Assuming a drop-out rate of 20%, we need to include 1223 subjects. The multicentric protocol includes 2,000 subjects (400 per country). Supposing the 20% loss to follow-up between T0 and T1 due to mortality, rehousing or impossibility to participate, we intend to receive complete data of 2000 participants at T1, which will bring about a sufficient power to analyze the primary and the secondary objectives.

Data management and statistical analysis

Data from all pilot sites will be combined and data-management and analysis will be done at the Erasmus University Medical Center in the Netherlands. Paper questionnaires will be transferred into electronic files and checked for missing or incorrect data. If an error is present in the electronic data, paper questionnaires are consulted. If needed, responsible staff is contacted for clarification. All data is handled confidentially and scientific data is stored anonymously.

In addition to descriptive statistics, tests for normal distribution of the outcome measures, risk factors and social determinants will be performed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Differences between T0 and T1 measurements will be assessed by means of the paired t-test (for variables showing a normal distribution), the Mann Whitney U test (for variables not normally distributed) or Pearson Chi-square test (for variable fractions). To determine the relationship of an outcome measure (T1) with explanatory variables, we will use an Ordinary Least Squares regression analysis for continuous outcome variables

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with the outcome measure (T0) and (change in) other outcome measures, risk factors and social determinants as explanatory variables. Logistic regression is performed for dichotomous outcome variables. In addition, the above-mentioned analyses will be repeated for each pilot site separately, for different risk groups as identified by the Selfy-MPI and possibly for other subgroups based on variables which are likely to influence the effect of the intervention itself, e.g. age or sex.

Using the baseline measurement as control group, a preliminary cost-effectiveness analysis will be performed from a societal and healthcare perspective and with a time horizon of 6 months. Healthcare costs for individual participants will be determined by multiplying resource use (doctor appointments, hospital emergency rooms and hospital admissions) with corresponding unit prices for 2017. Productivity losses for individual participants (lost productivity at paid work due to absenteeism and lost productivity at unpaid work) will follow from the PCQ. Utility values will be obtained through the EQ-5D-5L instrument.

Finally, a budget impact analysis (BIA) will estimate the financial consequences of implementing the intervention. BIA are very valuable in supporting the adoption of policies for the prevention of chronic conditions because they take accessibility and affordability constraints into account when considering cost effectiveness. To estimate the societal cost savings (or economic burden) of the CDSMP intervention, the mean societal costs per participant will be extrapolated to the prevalence of the target population in respective countries.

Data Protection

Data processing, communication and transfer will be carried out in accordance with the local data protection obligations of all participating study sites, as well as national and European requirements (EU Directive 96/46 on data protection). Participants are separately informed about data security in the participant's information letter.

As of May 25th 2018, this is being done in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. The new regulation requires that users must be clearly informed about the extent of data collection, the legal basis for processing of personal data, how long data is retained, if data is being transferred to a third-party and/or outside the EU, and disclosure of any automated decision-making (not applicable in EFFICHRONIC). Users must be provided with contact details for data management and be informed of their rights under the GDPR.

At any time, participants can exercise their data protection rights. Only the research team and the health authorities (if applicable), who have the duty to maintain confidentiality, will have access to all collected study data. Only information that cannot be identified may be transmitted to third parties. In the event of information transmission to other countries, it will be carried out anonymously with a data protection level according to the Regulation (EU) 2016/679. The data will be collected and preserved until the study is finished in a codified way. The person responsible for data custody is responsible for the data file and treatment. At the end of the study, the data will be anonymized.

3.2 CDSMP IMPLEMENTATION

CDSMP Programme

The CDSMP programme consists of a series of 6 tightly scripted workshops, 2.5 hours each, which are held once a week for 6 weeks. The content of each session is detailed in the Leaders' manual, including the interactions of the Leaders with the participants. The sessions can not be shortened or their content redistributed over a different number of sessions. The intervention can be delivered by professionals (such as health professionals, care professionals and NGOs volunteers or employees) as well as by trained lay-persons (other citizens with a chronic condition or informal carers) and is attended by a group of citizens with different chronic conditions and caregivers. The workshops are facilitated face-to-face with a total of 10-15 people per group. In all pilot sites, every series of 6 workshops will preferably be led by a professional and a lay person together. To this end, professionals and lay persons are recruited and trained in the CDSMP principles in the local language.

The sessions are based on techniques to overcome problems such as frustration, fatigue, pain and isolation and it includes some practical exercises on several topics, such as

- maintaining and improving physical strength, flexibility and resistance
- making an adequate use of medications
- promoting effective communication with family, friends and health professionals
- promoting healthy eating
- evaluating the use of alternative treatments

The program is based on the self-efficacy theory and emphasizes three process capabilities: problem solving, decision making and confidence building. The secret of the programme's effectiveness lies in the process of the highly participative sessions. Both mutual support and success in achieving goals foster the confidence of the participants in their ability to manage their health and keep an active and enjoyable life.

Each participant in the workshop receives a participant's handout and a reference to the book "Taking Control of your Health", that can be consulted in libraries or other public places.

Following the 2019 SMRC² Implementation Manual, there are some necessary elements to consider before implementing the programme. The most relevant elements are: the SMRC CDSMP license, the Leaders' training according to the CSDMP methodology, the preparation of the material and the quality control of the workshops by auditing Leaders. Each aspect is further explained in the next section.

² The Self-Management Resource Center replaces the The Stanford Patient Education Research Center, dedicated to helping improve health status and self-management skills. <https://www.selfmanagementresource.com/>

SMRC CDSMP license

All organizations (such as non-profit organizations or public agencies) that offer any of the SMRC programmes and that organize Leaders training must have a programme-specific license.

The CDSMP-specific SMRC license allows the concerned organization to facilitate the programme once Leaders have been trained. Holding the license also implies following the CDSMP Fidelity Manual, to ensure programme delivery as designed and safeguard quality of the evidence-based programme.

In EFFICHRONIC, the license has been acquired individually by each partner from the beginning of the training. Vively³, the representative of the Self-Management Resource Centre in Europe and who as part of the External Advisory Board of the project, negotiated for all partners the specific rates associated to the training needs for EFFICHRONIC.

CDSMP Training

The training of people with chronic conditions and caregivers for the CDSMP takes place following a strict training manual. The CDSMP training is done according to a cascade training model (figure 1): on the highest level are SMRC trainers who train T-trainers, who in their turn train Master trainers, who then train Leaders. The Leaders facilitate the workshops in the community. Trainings at all levels of the cascade are conducted by pairs. Ideally in EFFICHRONIC, each pair of Leaders should consist of at least one lay-person suffering from a chronic condition or a caregiver. The other Leader may be a health professional, city council staff or member of an association or NGO. Professional Leaders are not to reveal their background to the participants to maintain the peer-to-peer atmosphere of the sessions.

Figure 1. Training chain of the CDSMP

³ <https://vively.es/>

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There are two different ways for any organization to dispose of Leaders to facilitate the programme in the community:

- **Train Master Trainers** first at the proper organization. Highly qualified trainers (T-Trainers) from another organization carry out a 5 day training to teach Master Trainers based on a strict protocol. To complete the training, these Master trainers must carry out a minimum of three CDSMP workshops as Leaders in the community in the year following their training, before they can instruct Leaders themselves. Having trained Master trainers belonging to the proper organization, the organization itself can instruct Leaders, as detailed below, to facilitate the programme whenever needed.

- **Train only Leaders** or monitors within the organization borrowing Master trainers from another organization. A four-day protocolized Leaders training is carried out in groups of about 20 people. The Leaders complete their training by facilitating a course in the community, which must be audited by a Master Trainer or another person from the organization who is familiar with the programme. If the result of the training and audit is positive, the person receives the certification of Leader of the CDSMP programme.

Material

Different types of material are necessary to carry out the CDSMP workshops. The Leaders need their Leader's manual and 30 teaching charts to facilitate the programme in the community. The end-users need the student's dossier, the CDs of physical exercise and relaxation (depending on the country), and access to the book "Living a Healthy Life with Chronic Conditions" in the language of the corresponding country.

Quality Control

T-Trainers, Master Trainers or trained Leaders from the research team (where the previous are not available) in each organization are in charge of ensuring the quality of the training according to the terms of the SMRC license.

In order to ensure the quality standards and the results of this evidence-based programme, which has successfully been running since 30 years, it is necessary to strictly follow the programme's manual and the training cascade. All Leaders facilitating workshops in the community must be audited by T-Trainers, Master Trainers or trained Leaders from the research team.

The audit of the workshops must consider the following aspects:

- The features of the room. It must be possible to accommodate up to 20 people in a circle or U shape and it must provide enough space for the Leaders, participants, flip charts, white board, and still have room to move around. Also, lighting, sound and temperature conditions must be assessed as well as availability of parking space and being near public transport. Easy access for the handicapped must be available if necessary.
- The skills of the Leader: programme fidelity (including chart presentation), ability to facilitate all the programme group activities (brainstorming, action plans, problem solving, sharing experiences and

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decision-making, ability to manage group dynamics, judge situations and deal with difficult participants are being evaluated. Punctuality and good collaboration with the co-leader are also desirable features.

Implementation of the CDSMP in EFFICHRONIC

The implementation of the CDSMP programme is being carried out strictly as described before.

An intensive communication campaign has been carried out to foster the recruitment of the target vulnerable populations. This strategy is described in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3.

To better understand the results in the corresponding section of this deliverable, it is convenient to understand different concepts that relate to the description of the implementation results of EFFICHRONIC:

- **Engaged people:** People that signed up for the programme and that attended at least one out of six sessions.
- **People who have completed the CDSMP:** Participants that have completed the programme successfully. These are participants that attended a minimum of four out of six sessions of the programme.
- **People who have completed the questionnaire.** These are participants that completed the CDSMP (minimum four sessions) and that filled out the questionnaires properly.

SECTION 4: RESULTS

4.1 EVALUATION RESULTS

The results of the evaluation process in relation to the objectives set in section 2 are as follows:

1. Collaboration from all partners to define the evaluative framework

A systematic review of the literature and the measurement instruments previously proposed in the Grant Agreement are the basis for a first evaluation proposal. Subsequently, a national discussion with a panel of experts in evaluation and implementation of self-management programmes from different countries took place. Different perspectives from different regions with different stages of development of the programme were included. The SMRC team (members of the Advisory Board) provided feedback to improve the protocols. The EFFICHRONIC partners reviewed and approved the final evaluation framework by consensus.

2. Elaboration of the baseline and follow-up questionnaires using the validated scales

The information collected by means of these questionnaires are to answer the research questions of the EFFICHRONIC project as reflected in the objectives of this deliverable (Section 2). The questionnaires can be found in Annex 1 and 2. The questionnaires have been elaborated based on the following outcomes: health indicators, health behaviour, self-efficacy, quality of life and use of the health care services. Figures 2, 3 and 4 show the sequence of the evaluation objectives, as well as the correlation of the measured parameters in relation to the objectives and the final scales used for measuring the outcomes (see section 3.1 for additional information). The questionnaires were translated in the corresponding language of the participating countries.

Figure 2. EFFICHRONIC Research questions

Part 1 – Answer Q1 (Baseline and 6-month follow-up)	Healthy lifestyle; Depression; Sleep and fatigue; Adherence to medications; Self-efficacy; Health-related quality of life
Part 2 – Answer Q2 (Baseline and 6-month follow-up)	The prevalence of experienced medical errors; Communication with healthcare providers; Health literacy
Part 3 – Answer Q3 (Baseline and 6-month follow-up)	Healthcare utilization; Productivity losses
Part 4 – Answer Q4 (6-month follow-up)	Experience of the specific elements; Health system; Communication skills; Satisfaction of the CDSMP intervention
Part 5– Socio-demographic variables (Baseline and partly 6-month follow-up)	Age; Gender; Country of birth; Educational level; Employment situation

Figure 3. EFFICHRONIC Evaluation framework: Objectives and main domains

Domains	Instruments
Healthy lifestyle (Physical exercise, Healthy eating, Sedentary behaviour, Smoking, Alcohol use)	Exercise Behaviour scale, International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ), AUDIT-C
Depression	Patient Health Questionnaire depression scale (PHQ-8)
Sleep and fatigue	Visual analog scale (0-10)
Adherence to medications	Short Medication Adherence Questionnaire (SMAQ)
Self-efficacy	Chronic Disease Self-Efficacy instrument (CDSE-6)
Health-related quality of life (HRQoL)	12-item short-form (SF-12), Euroqol (EQ-5D-5L)
Prevalence of experienced medical errors	American Association of Retired Persons (AARP) 'survey beyond 50.09' questionnaire
Communication with healthcare providers	3 items Communication with healthcare providers
Health literacy	Health Literacy Questionnaire (HLQ)
Healthcare utilization (Doctor appointments, Use of hospital emergency rooms, Hospital admissions)	SMRC Health Care Utilization questionnaire
Productivity losses (Lost productivity at paid work due to absenteeism; Lost productivity at unpaid work)	Productivity Costs Questionnaire (PCQ)
Experience of the specific elements (Problem solving, Decision making, Confidence building)	5 point Likert scale (disagree-agree)
Participants' confidence in their national health system	5 point Likert scale (disagree-agree)
Improvement of interpersonal communication skills	5 point Likert scale (disagree-agree)
Satisfaction with the whole CDSMP intervention	Visual analog scale (0-10)

Figure 4. EFFICHRONIC evaluation framework: Main domains and evaluation tools

3. The development of a protocol for data collection and analysis

Data collection meets the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679. The database and statistical analysis plan have been created by the Erasmus Medical Center in the Netherlands and is described in the methodology section.

4.2 IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

This deliverable presents the implementation results obtained up to M24 and focuses on the outcomes of the tasks 5.2 (Preparation of the Intervention) and 5.3 (Implementation of the CDSMP). The implementation of the programme began in August 2018 (M14) and is expected to finish in September 2019 (M28).

1. Preparation of the intervention

The first results are related to the process of preparing the material for the intervention and conducting the CDSMP Leaders training. The training materials for Leaders and participants were prepared in the five languages of the EFFICHRONIC consortium: English, French, Italian, Spanish and Dutch. In Spain, the UK and Italy, no extra work was necessary for EFFICHRONIC as the CDSMP programme was already being implemented before the start of the project and available in each of the corresponding languages. However, In France, all the educational material for Leaders and participants needed to be adapted from the Canadian French version and in the Netherlands the material had to be translated to Dutch. Subsequently, all translations and adaptations were by the SMRC.

The second results of the preparation phase refer to the training of Leaders. One of the objectives of EFFICHRONIC, as included in the Grant Agreement, is to train 32 Leaders at each of the five pilot sites, i.e., a total of 160 Leaders for the whole project.

The different starting points of each partner regarding CDSMP experience and available resources have given rise to the different forms of obtaining the required number of CDSMP Leaders for EFFICHRONIC:

- In the UK, it was not necessary to train Master Trainers or Leaders specifically for EFFICHRONIC as there is a large existing network of CDSMP providers and certified Leaders. Furthermore, there is a variety of available providers serving different kinds of populations, including vulnerable populations. So, the efforts of the EFFICHRONIC team in the UK focused on contacting and negotiating with different providers to agree on participating in EFFICHRONIC.
- Asturias has a team of two trained T-Trainers who instruct Master trainers and Leaders in an autonomous way.
- The strategy of France has been to firstly train Master Trainers belonging to their organization. Three French Master Trainers were instructed by the Asturian T-Trainers. On their turn, these Master Trainers have carried out two training sessions in France to instruct sufficient Leaders to facilitate the programme in the community.
- In Genoa, Italy, 4 certified Master Trainers with more than ten years of experience were contracted to train two groups of Leaders.

- In the Netherlands, Leaders were also trained directly by “borrowed” Master trainers. Two master trainers from Asturias provided a Leaders training in Rotterdam, and 2 local Master trainers instructed Leaders in 3 occasions.

More details on the Leaders training can be found in Table 1:

Table 1. CDSMP Leaders trainings in the five EFFICHRONIC countries

Country	Type	Date	Trained people	Total Certified
France	Master Trainer	March 2018	3 Master Trainers	3 Master Trainers 32 Leaders
	Leader	June 2018	17 Leaders	
	Leader	Aug - Sept 2018	15 Leaders	
The Netherlands	Leader	March 2018	4 Leaders	32 Leaders
	Leader	July 2018	15 Leaders	
	Leader	Sept 2018	5 Leaders	
	Leader	Jan 2019	9 Leaders	
Italy	Leader	Nov 2017	20 Leaders	36 Leaders
	Leader	Nov 2018	16 Leaders	
Spain	Master Trainer	March 2018	16 Master Trainers	3 Master Trainers 41 Leaders
	Leader	Jan 2018	8 Leaders	
	Leader	June 2018	11 Leaders	
	Leader	Oct 2018	8 Leaders	
	Leader	Jan 2019	14 Leaders	
UK	Not applicable, network already available			32+ Leaders

Each partner of the consortium has trained a minimum of 32 Leaders which are needed to implement the educational programme. It is worth mentioning that this has been achieved by the different types of organizations that participate in EFFICHRONIC (such as health care systems or public entities) in countries with diverse cultural and political environments and different starting points. In addition, the quality requirements of the CDSMP methodology have been fulfilled by all the partners. The EFFICHRONIC partner in the UK works with the following CDSMP providers that already have certified Leaders:

- BME United, that works with black and ethnic minorities people in Birmingham
- Public Health Wales, that provides the intervention programme in North Wales

- Northern Ireland Chest, Heart and Stroke: a specialised charity that works with population affected by specific conditions
- Talking Therapies, an NHS organization in East London
- Citizens Advice South Derbyshire, a charity in an deprived area
- Action Heart, a West Midlands organization in another area of vulnerability.

2. Implementation Results

The intermediary results at M24 regarding the implementation of the intervention are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. EFFICHRONIC CDSMP workshops and assistants in the five countries at M24

Country	Number of completed CDSMP workshops	Number of engaged ⁴ people in the CDSMP	People currently in a CDSMP (in M24)	Number of people who completed a CDSMP	Number of baseline questionnaires filled in	Number of Selfy-MPI questionnaires filled in ⁵
France	13	111	6	96 ⁶	96 ⁶	96 ⁶
Italy	19	238	21	170	170	145
The Netherlands	10	105	22	83	43	5
Spain	40	473	112	413	309	248
UK	20	323	50	280	140	138
		1250	211			
TOTAL	102	1461		1042	758	631

The trainings in the UK, France and Spain are audited by certified Master Trainers. In Italy, a trained Leader, member of the Galliera Hospital research team is in charge of the audits. In the Netherlands, both the Master trainer and a trained Leader from the research team audit Leaders while facilitating the workshops with end-users.

⁴ See p17 for the definitions

⁵ Caregivers do not complete the Selfy-MPI questionnaire

⁶ Data from 12 workshops

In EFFICHRONIC, the programme is being carried out in retirement homes, patients associations, immigrants and social centers, and prisons among other locations.

4.3 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were established in the project's Grant Agreement.

Table 3 shows the KPIs that are used to measure the outcomes of the specific objective 3: "To implement the programme in the 5 region countries, including the appropriate measures to involve at least 400 individuals of the stratified / identified populations in each setting (N = 2000). This specific objective corresponds to WP5 (task 5.2 and 5.3). It is worth mentioning that the implementation has not finished yet and is expected to be completed by M28.

Table 3. EFFICHRONIC: KPI related to the specific objective 3 (task 5.2 and 5.3) at M24 (provisional data)

CSDMP Implementation	Target	Achieved	%
Individuals reached during the communication-recruitment phase	200.000	906.000 ⁷	100%
Individuals engaged in EFFICHRONIC (400 per country)	2000	1461	73,1%
Individuals trained in EFFICHRONIC (400 per country)	2000	1042	52,1%
Countries where EFFICHRONIC is implemented	5	5	100%
Facilitators recruited (32 per country)	160	>160	100%
Patients suffering from or at risk at chronic disease recruited	2000	1461	73,1%
Global learning outcomes. Percentage of successful accomplishment	80%	83,4%	100%
Experimental mortality rate	<20%	16,6%	100%

The "individuals engaged" in EFFICHRONIC refers to the percentage of people that attend at least one session of the programme. The individuals trained are the people that completed four out of six sessions. The expected success rate obtained is 83.4% which is higher than expected (80%). This percentage refers to the number of individuals that completed the programme (1042) with respect to the total number of engaged people before M24 (N=1250). As a consequence, the experimental mortality rate is 16.6%, which will probably increase taking into account the future drop-out rate when collecting the follow-up questionnaires.

The KPIs related to the specific objective 4 ("To generate a comprehensive framework for the impact assessment -including cost-efficiency and health economics techniques- and implement specific

⁷ This is a rough estimate. Data from the General Mass Media Survey could not be obtained

methodologies to provide evidence-based comparative data on the effectiveness and efficiency of the investment in such preventive and management empowerment programs in a specific population”) are shown in Table 4. This specific objective corresponds to WP6 (Task 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3).

Table 4.EFFICHRONIC: KPI related to specific objective 4 (Task 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3) at M24

Evaluation	Target	Achieved	%
Number of patients-intervention tested*	2000	758	37,9%
Health Economics dimensions assessed	3	3	100%
Socioeconomic and sociocultural dimensions assessed	10	10	100%
Clinical/medical specific dimensions assessed	8	8	100%
Framework for effectiveness and cost-efficiency evaluation	1	1	100%

The clinical and economic dimensions have been described in the methodology section of this deliverable. The social dimensions that were also included in the Selfy-MPI have been explained in deliverable D4.1: "List of clinical and social variables and MPI index".

Analysing the results, it is evident that the low completion percentage of the evaluation questionnaires (= number of patients-interventions tested*) needs some attention. All consortium partners are encountering important difficulties to get the questionnaires completed. This fact is most likely related to the characteristics of the target group of this project. In the groups where the criteria of social vulnerability are loneliness, isolation or even social exclusion, a higher percentage of completion is found, while in ethnic minorities or immigrants, the difficulties to receive completed questionnaires are more important.

The coordinator team analyzed the reasons for this low completion and identified the following: refusal to sign the informed consent, lack of willingness to complete any kind of questionnaire regardless its nature or extent, and distrust because of questions that are perceived as intrusive (e.g income). The team also consulted the matter with Kate Lorig⁸, who attended the consortium meeting in Rotterdam on May 3rd 2019. She provided valuable suggestions such as involving people from the proper community to collect the questionnaires or organize data collection through phonecalls.

Nevertheless, the statistical calculation of the sample size as described in section 3, determined that 978 is the number of needed completed follow-up questionnaires to ensure statistical power. Taking into account that the average number of trained people with filled-in questionnaires per month is 75 by month 24 (758 questionnaires from M14 to M24), the provision is to have 300 more participants by M28, the end date for implementation. This would increase the total number of completed questionnaires to 1236. Even taking into account a drop-out rate of 20% regarding the expected number of follow-up questionnaires, this would ensure a sufficiently large sample size to provide statistical power to evaluate the results of EFFICHRONIC.

⁸ Kate Lorig is the Director of the Self-Management Resource Centre and the founder of the CDSMP. She is also member of the EFFICHRONIC External Advisory Board

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SECTION 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

The evaluation study aims to appraise the potential benefits of the CDSMP intervention for citizens with a chronic condition and caregivers with a low SEP in terms of self-management related to healthy lifestyle, emotions, medication adherence and HR-QoL. This study has several strengths. To our knowledge this is one of the first European studies that aims to implement an evidence-based intervention specifically in citizens with a low SEP, an understudied population which experiences more adverse chronic conditions and fewer opportunities and possibilities to adhere to healthy habits. Recruiting the target population in different settings will provide information on the generalizability of the approach in various European settings. This could generate a wider acceptance of the CDSMP intervention and facilitate implementation of other health surveys, interventions and health programmes in this type of population. Furthermore, cost-effectiveness data regarding self-management programmes are limited. The EFFICHRONIC project will provide insight into potential societal cost savings resulting from a reduction in healthcare utilization and productivity losses.

The study also has some limitations and we expect to encounter various challenges. Firstly, having citizens with a low SEP to participate may be a problem that could affect the five countries in a different manner. Recruiting participants can be organized in different ways according to availability and organizational structures in the local context. Therefore, it is valuable to evaluate the effectiveness of approaches in different (international) settings. Secondly, it was not practicable to include a control group. To avoid that a citizen with a low SEP would feel excluded, we prefer to offer the intervention to all citizens with a low SEP that meet our criteria. We apply a pre-post design with measurement moments at two points in time: at baseline (T0) and after 6 months (T1). The preliminary cost-effectiveness analysis will be performed using the baseline measurement as the 'control value'. Thirdly, to perform a thorough evaluation of an intervention, a lot of data need to be collected. Nevertheless, we had to trade-off the number of questions in our questionnaire because of the difficulties citizens with a low SEP may have answering the questions. In our questionnaire we tried to capture the most important risk factors; however, it is likely that we missed relevant variables.

As the high prevalence of chronic conditions will pose a challenge for European health systems, new ways of achieving sustainable health systems are necessary. Increasing the ability of citizens with a chronic condition to take care of themselves for as long as possible may provide better outcomes. The EFFICHRONIC project will further elucidate whether such an approach could be feasible and (cost-) effective for populations with a chronic condition and with a low SEP in different settings.

5.2 CDSMP IMPLEMENTATION

An important achievement regarding the implementation has been the elaboration of adapted and translated CDSMP training material. In EFFICHRONIC, three partners (UK, Italy and Spain) had already the material translated into their language. In France, an adaptation of the Canadian version of the materials was necessary whereas in the Netherlands a full translation was made. A first conclusion is that some extra time was needed to elaborate the materials in countries where the programme was not previously implemented. As a consequence, the available time to implement the programme has been

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reduced drastically at these particular study sites. This explains, among other reasons, the different recruitment results and number of trained participants.

Potential Leaders are often selected among the participants of workshops in the community. It concerns participants trained in the CDSMP methodology who feel confident enough to provide the training themselves. However, in France, Italy and the Netherlands this is more difficult as the intervention programme had not been implemented previously to EFFICHRONIC. Notwithstanding, all the partners have achieved the minimum number of trained Leaders to ensure the successful implementation of the workshops. Also, it is worth mentioning that the programme has been implemented in a reasonable time framework: all EFFICHRONIC partners finished the Leaders training by month 18 of the project.

Although the implementation phase has not yet been completed, another important conclusion is that the dissemination strategies have been successful to reach and recruit the target population.

The big difference in recruitment percentages between countries is heavily determined by the availability or not of previously implemented programmes and trained Leaders. Therefore, it is recommended that future studies related to the implementation of the CDSMP, or for that matter, any kind of programme, take into account the different stages of actual development of the programme at the implicated study sites and to calculate and / or distribute the sample size of the target population in a more realistic way.

Another important finding is the low level of completion of the questionnaires in the vulnerable population. Nevertheless, it is not because they haven't filled out any questionnaire, they haven't profited from the intervention and can't supply important data for EFFICHRONIC. For this reason, it is considered necessary to also conduct qualitative studies in the target population. This will help to assess the impact of the intervention on those people with special vulnerability where the collection of information through a questionnaire has not been possible. In addition, a profound causal analysis of the reasons for not completing the questionnaires is necessary.

In this deliverable, the evaluative framework has been presented and all the necessary dimensions and variables have been successfully included to ensure both cost-effectiveness and health impact evaluation. Also, the strengths and weaknesses linked to the CDSMP implementation have been discussed in detail for each member country.

To conclude, the data collected from the pilots until M24 are providing the first insights on the implementation of the CDSMP in vulnerable population at European level. Although less data have been collected than planned in the project proposal, the implementation is evolving well thanks to the big efforts of all consortium members. Additional efforts will be made during the final phase of the implementation, especially by the members with the lowest number of included participants, by hiring more staff, train more Leaders and increase communication and dissemination activities.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. WHO: Global status report on noncommunicable diseases 2014. In. Switzerland; 2014.
2. WHO: Global action plan for the prevention and control of NCDs 2013-2020. In. Switzerland; 2013.
3. Dahlgreen G, Whitehead M: Policies and strategies to promote social equity in health. Stockholm: Institute of Future Studies; 1991.
4. Sambamoorthi U, Tan X, Deb A: Multiple chronic conditions and healthcare costs among adults. *Expert Rev Pharmacoecon Outcomes Res* 2015, 15(5):823-832.
5. Collaborators GBDRF: Global, regional, and national comparative risk assessment of 79 behavioural, environmental and occupational, and metabolic risks or clusters of risks, 1990-2015: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015. *Lancet* 2016, 388(10053):1659-1724.
6. Lin CC, Tsai FM, Lin HS, Hwang SJ, Chen HC: Effects of a self-management program on patients with early-stage chronic kidney disease: a pilot study. *Appl Nurs Res* 2013, 26(3):151-156.
7. Jonker AA, Comijs HC, Knipscheer KC, Deeg DJ: Promotion of self-management in vulnerable older people: a narrative literature review of outcomes of the Chronic Disease Self-Management Program (CDSMP). *Eur J Ageing* 2009, 6(4):303-314.
8. Paone D: Factors Supporting Implementation among CDSMP Organizations. *Front Public Health* 2014, 2:237.
9. Liddy C, Johnston S, Guilcher S, Irving H, Hogel M, Jaglal S: Impact of a chronic disease self-management program on healthcare utilization in eastern Ontario, Canada. *Prev Med Rep* 2015, 2:586-590.
10. Ahn S, Basu R, Smith ML, Jiang L, Lorig K, Whitelaw N, Ory MG: The impact of chronic disease self-management programs: healthcare savings through a community-based intervention. *BMC Public Health* 2013, 13:1141.
11. Horrell LN, Kneipp SM: Strategies for recruiting populations to participate in the chronic disease self-management program (CDSMP): A systematic review. *Health Mark Q* 2017, 34(4):268-283.
12. Teuscher D, Bukman AJ, van Baak MA, Feskens EJM, Renes RJ, Meershoek A: A lifestyle intervention study targeting individuals with low socioeconomic status of different ethnic origins: important aspects for successful implementation. *BMC Public Health* 2017, 18(1):54.
13. Thompson FE, McNeel TS, Dowling EC, Midthune D, Morrisette M, Zeruto CA: Interrelationships of added sugars intake, socioeconomic status, and race/ethnicity in adults in the United States: National Health Interview Survey, 2005. *J Am Diet Assoc* 2009, 109(8):1376-1383.
14. de Munter JS, Agyemang C, van Valkengoed IG, Bhopal R, Zaninotto P, Nazroo J, Kunst AE, Stronks K: Cross national study of leisure-time physical activity in Dutch and English populations with ethnic group comparisons. *Eur J Public Health* 2013, 23(3):440-446.
15. Marshall SJ, Jones DA, Ainsworth BE, Reis JP, Levy SS, Macera CA: Race/ethnicity, social class, and leisure-time physical inactivity. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 2007, 39(1):44-51.
16. Ejiogu N, Norbeck JH, Mason MA, Cromwell BC, Zonderman AB, Evans MK: Recruitment and retention strategies for minority or poor clinical research participants: lessons from the Healthy Aging in Neighborhoods of Diversity across the Life Span study. *Gerontologist* 2011, 51 Suppl 1:S33-45.
17. Articles about the Chronic Disease Self-Management Program
[<https://www.selfmanagementresource.com/resources/bibliography/cdsmp>]
18. Lorig KR, Sobel DS, Ritter PL, Laurent D, Hobbs M: Effect of a self-management program on patients with chronic disease. *Eff Clin Pract* 2001, 4(6):256-262.
19. Ory MG, Ahn S, Jiang L, Lorig K, Ritter P, Laurent DD, Whitelaw N, Smith ML: National study of chronic disease self-management: six-month outcome findings. *J Aging Health* 2013, 25(7):1258-1274.

20. Pilotto A, Daragjati J, Veronese N: CGA and Clinical Decision-Making: The Multidimensional Prognostic Index. In: Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment. edn. Edited by Pilotto A, Martin FC. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2018: 79-92.
21. Garcia-Caselles P, Miralles R, Arellano M, Torres RM, Aguilera A, Pi-Figueras M, Cervera AM: Validation of a modified version of the Gijón's social-familial evaluation scale (SFES): the "Barcelona SFES Version", for patients with cognitive impairment. *Arch Gerontol Geriatr Suppl* 2004(9):201-206.
22. Booth M: Assessment of physical activity: an international perspective. *Res Q Exerc Sport* 2000, 71 Suppl 2:114-120.
23. Bush K, Kivlahan DR, McDonnell MB, Fihn SD, Bradley KA: The AUDIT alcohol consumption questions (AUDIT-C): an effective brief screening test for problem drinking. Ambulatory Care Quality Improvement Project (ACQUIP). Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test. *Arch Intern Med* 1998, 158(16):1789-1795.
24. Kroenke K, Strine TW, Spitzer RL, Williams JB, Berry JT, Mokdad AH: The PHQ-8 as a measure of current depression in the general population. *J Affect Disord* 2009, 114(1-3):163-173.
25. Ortega Suarez FJ, Sanchez Plumed J, Perez Valentin MA, Pereira Palomo P, Munoz Cepeda MA, Lorenzo Aguiar D, Grupo de Estudio V: Validation on the simplified medication adherence questionnaire (SMAQ) in renal transplant patients on tacrolimus. *Nefrologia* 2011, 31(6):690-696.
26. Ware J, Jr., Kosinski M, Keller SD: A 12-Item Short-Form Health Survey: construction of scales and preliminary tests of reliability and validity. *Med Care* 1996, 34(3):220-233.
27. Brooks R: EuroQol: the current state of play. *Health Policy* 1996, 37(1):53-72.
28. Lorig K, Stewart A, Ritter P, González V, Laurent D, Lynch J: Outcome measures for health education and other health care interventions. Thousand Oaks CA, US: Sage Publications, Inc.; 1996.
29. Hawkins M, Gill SD, Batterham R, Elsworth GR, Osborne RH: The Health Literacy Questionnaire (HLQ) at the patient-clinician interface: a qualitative study of what patients and clinicians mean by their HLQ scores. *BMC Health Services Research* 2017, 17:309.
30. Bo A, Friis K, Osborne RH, Mairdal HT: National indicators of health literacy: ability to understand health information and to engage actively with healthcare providers - a population-based survey among Danish adults. *BMC Public Health* 2014, 14:1095.
31. Batterham RW, Buchbinder R, Beauchamp A, Dodson S, Elsworth GR, Osborne RH: The OPTimising HEalth LIterAcY (Ophelia) process: study protocol for using health literacy profiling and community engagement to create and implement health reform. *BMC Public Health* 2014, 14:694.
32. Lorig K, Ritter PL, Moreland C, Laurent DD: Can a Box of Mailed Materials Achieve the Triple Aims of Health Care? The Mailed Chronic Disease Self-Management Tool Kit Study. *Health Promot Pract* 2015, 16(5):765-774.
33. Bouwmans C, Krol M, Severens H, Koopmanschap M, Brouwer W, Hakkaart-van Roijen L: The iMTA Productivity Cost Questionnaire: A Standardized Instrument for Measuring and Valuing Health-Related Productivity Losses. *Value Health* 2015, 18(6):753-758.
34. Mahoney FI, Barthel DW: Functional Evaluation: The Barthel Index. *Md State Med J* 1965, 14:61-65.
35. Lawton MP, Brody EM: Assessment of older people: self-maintaining and instrumental activities of daily living. *Gerontologist* 1969, 9(3):179-186.
36. Brown J, Pengas G, Dawson K, Brown LA, Clatworthy P: Self administered cognitive screening test (TYM) for detection of Alzheimer's disease: cross sectional study. *BMJ* 2009, 338:b2030.
37. Rubenstein LZ, Harker JO, Salva A, Guigoz Y, Vellas B: Screening for undernutrition in geriatric practice: developing the short-form mini-nutritional assessment (MNA-SF). *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci* 2001, 56(6):M366-372.
38. Linn BS, Linn MW, Gurel L: Cumulative illness rating scale. *J Am Geriatr Soc* 1968, 16(5):622-626.
39. Haas M., Grouppe E., Muench J., Kraemer D., Brummel-Smith K., Sharma R., Ganger B., Attwood M., Fairweather A., Chronic Disease Self-Management Program for Low Back Pain in the Elderly. *Journal of Manipulative and Physiological Therapeutics*, 2005, 28 (4): 228-23.

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ANNEX 1 BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE

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ANNEX 2 FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONNAIRE